

PRESUPPOSITIONAL FEATURES OF IN LEXICAL UNITS USED IN A TEXT

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Abstract: The article addresses contemporary linguistic issues, with a specific focus on the phenomenon of presupposition and its integration into Uzbek linguistics as a nascent field. The examination extends to the utilization of lexical units associated with presupposition within the realm of pragmatics in literary works. The significance of presupposition-forming tools is underscored, particularly in the context of literary endeavors where their characteristics are more distinctly delineated.

Key words: *pragmatics, presupposition, metaphor, phonopragmatic implicature, metaphorical implicature, implicit, explicit, synonymous sequence, paralinguistic.*

Metaphors have been extensively examined in the context of Uzbek linguistics, as they represent a form of connotative shift. However, the clarification of their aspects related to the text has not yet been fully addressed. This is because the occurrence of metaphor in a text can be explained from various perspectives. Texts employing metaphors demonstrate that not only the conceptualization but also the expression of a specific situation can be grounded in metaphor. Based on this characteristic, metaphors can be categorized into those manifested as words, phrases, sentences, and entire texts. Professor D.S. Hudayberganova, who delved into this matter distinctly, introduced the terms "speech metaphors" and "text metaphors"¹ to the scientific discourse, providing a justified foundation for their exploration.

1. Linguistic and non-linguistic features of word-form metaphors have been thoroughly investigated in our linguistics.² However, their psycholinguistic and cognitive aspects are still awaiting exploration. Cognitive word-metaphors are primarily understood through the semantics of words denoting actions and symbols, implicitly conveying the concept of the object and event

¹ Худайбергенова Д.С. Ўзбек тилидаги бадиий матнларнинг антропоцентрик талқини. ф.ф.док. афтореферат – Тошкент, 1985. – Б. 124. / Khudaiberganova. Anthropocentric Rendering of Literary Texts in the Uzbek Language. Ph.D. dissertation abstract.

² Миртожиев М. Ўзбек тили семасиологияси. – Тошкент: Мумтоз сўз, 2010. – Б. 98. / Mirtojiev, M. Semiology of the Uzbek Language.

being compared. For instance, phrases in Uzbek like 'Gapi uzilib qoldi' (his words were cut), 'Gapi cho'zilib ketdi' (his words expanded), and 'Gapni ulab yubordi' (he connected it with his words) exemplify the figurative use of verbs, suggesting that, in their semantics, the author's words are likened to entities like a thread or a rope. Such words and metaphors are prevalent in our language. For instance, emotion is portrayed as an adversary, emotion is akin to a written expression. In our language, emotions and feelings are metaphorically likened to the waves of the sea, a river, or an ocean. Consider this example:

U birda **yoprilib** kelgan bu **tuvg'uni** zo'rg'a **yengib**, saraybonga "darvozoni qoq", deb imo qildi ("Ulug' xazina"). (He struggled to overcome this sudden surge of emotion and gestured to the palace security to "knock on the gate" ("The Great Treasure")).

Bilamis yuragining bir chetida hamon iliq **hislar miltirab turardi**. Yuragidagi isyonkor **tuvg'ular** asta-sekin **so'nib**, hayolini allaqanday ma'yus o'ylar band etdi. (Bilamis still harbored warm feelings flickering in one corner of his heart. It seemed as if the rebellious emotions in his heart gradually waned, giving way to gloomy thoughts occupying his imagination).

The manifestations of implicature in the Uzbek language are scientifically studied in a monographic context. In this regard, Professors N. Mahmudov, A. Nurmanov, Sh. Safarov, and M. Hakimova have contributed their perspectives.

The implicature in the Uzbek literary language is pragmatically examined and divided into several types:³ phonopragmatic, stylistic pragmatic, metaphorical, individual, expressive, monologic, etc.

1. Phonopragmatic implicature is associated with the tone of the speaker's pronunciation. In this context, the speaker utters elements of the propositional act in the text with a specific, empirically determined tone. The speaker endeavors to convey the meaning of 'I am like that' to the listener, placing special emphasis on the pronunciation of the text. In the phonopragmatic perspective of implicature, the overall content of the text takes a secondary role. For instance, Marg'ilonga shom vaqtida kirgan edim, ko'zlagan joyimni topolmay adashdim (I entered Margilon town at dusk and lost my way).

- Qani bo'lmasa, juring biznikiga, mehmon, - aytkuchining so'z ohangidan o'rtoqlik bo'yi kelib Otabekning dimog'iga urdi. (A.Q) (- Then let me take you to our guesthouse," came the speaker's words, imbued with a sense of friendship that struck Otabek profoundly (Abdulla

³ Ҳакимов М. Ўзбек тилида матннинг прагматик талқини. Филол.фан.док.дисс. автореферати. – Тошкент., 2001. – Б. 34. / Hakimov M. Pragmatic interpretation of the text in Uzbek.

Qodiriy)). In this text, it is evident that the speaker's message conveys the heartfelt invitation to their home, characterized by the metaphorical scent of friendship⁴.

Within certain manifestations of phonopragmatic implicature, the pronunciation of a proposition through the emphatic manner of speech in some forms of conative expressions results in the conveyance of a distinctive tone, expressing sincerity in that specific context.

2. In the metaphorical implicature, a speaker indicates information structures by presenting a proposition based on the resemblance of the recipient to specific objects or subjects.

For example, A. Qahhor compares Saida to a bird called a titmouse: - Kolxo‘zni opichlab katta qilgansiz! Kolxo‘zning dardi qayerda, qitig‘i qayerda ekanini yaxshi bilasiz! “Bo‘ston”ga o‘xshagan kolxo‘zlardan o‘ntasini bitta sinchalog‘ingiz bilan ko‘tarasiz! ... Sinchalak degan qushni bilasizmi, oyog‘i ipday... Shu qush “osmon tushib ketsa ushlab qolaman” deb oyog‘ini ko‘tarib yotar ekan! (A.Q) (You've managed the collective farm! You know well the pains and tickles of the collective farm! With one little finger, you could raise ten collective farms like 'Boston'! ... Do you know the bird called a titmouse, whose leg is like a thread? This bird lies with its leg raised, saying, 'If the sky falls, I will hold it!' (A.Q.))

In the same scenario, within the novel 'Bazar' by H. Dostmuhammad, the author draws parallels between the bazar and a 'dragon' and 'crocodile'. The actions, life, and events depicted in the bazar resemble those of a dragon in a fairy tale. It is depicted as a dragon breathing fire and a 'crocodile' that engulfs everything in one gulp. The expression of such metaphorical meaning in the text is intricately tied to the speaker's inner goal and the writer's descriptive method, enhancing the impact of the writer's ideas. Consequently, it influences the listener's emotions and prompts a response. The propositional act within the metaphorical meaning formations consists of content resembling the described elements.

3. Personalized Implicature is specific only to the speech of certain individuals and serves to unveil their character. In such instances, the implicature employed by the speaker as a contextual reference is comprehensible to both the speaker and the listener but remains unknown to other participants in the conversation. For instance, - Birpas jimlikdan keyin Qalandarov gulzorning narigi tomonidagi idoraga qarab: - Eshon, hoy! deb chaqirdi. (A.Q.). (- After a brief silence, Kalandarov glanced at the office on the opposite side of the flower garden and exclaimed, 'Eshon, hey!' (A.Q.)). The act of calling and shouting in this manner carries a

⁴ Ҳақимов М. Ўзбек прагмалингвистикаси асослари. – Тошкент: Академнашр, 2013. – Б 100. / Hakimov M. Basics of Uzbek pragmalinguistics.

concealed individual meaning. Writers utilize such personal terms exclusively to illuminate the character and conduct of the depicted individual.

For instance, in the story 'Interrogation' by Kh. Dostmuhammad, which we are examining, Bazar witnessed the 'UFO.' Everyone was aware of it and questioned him. Only the chief accountant of the factory, Davletov, expressed his curiosity in this manner: - Ukkag'ar, anaular kelyaptimi? – Qizitaloqlar qanaqa gaplashadi? Odamga o'xshaganmi, o'zi, ularing? (Hey Ukkagar, are they coming? How do those bitch girls talk? Are they human-like?)

Bozor kulimsiradi? – Davletov kulimsiramadi. Aksincha, ... “Hoy, shayton!” deb Bozorga ishshaydi-da: “Mayli, boravur, bor” deb ko'chaga chiqarib ketdi. Davletov iljaymadi, tirjaymadi, balki ishshaydi – ayanchli ishshaydi va noilojlikdan, bola oldida nochor ko'rinishni o'ziga ep bilmaganidangina, “Mayli, boravur, bor” deya oldi. (Bazar smiled, but Davletov did not reciprocate. On the contrary, he addressed Bazar, saying 'Hey, Satan!' while revealing his white teeth. He then added, 'Okay, go, go,' and exited onto the street. Davletov didn't show any sign of flinching or smiling; instead, he grinned—miserably so. He did this solely because he couldn't bear to appear helpless in front of the boy, managing to say, 'Okay, go ahead, go.’)

In this dialogue, Davletov's distinctive behavior—his lack of inquiry into the story that captivates everyone, his failure to acknowledge Bazar as a child, his rudeness, and his unique individuality—are skillfully unveiled by the writer. As a result, the personalized implicature is applicable solely to the speech of certain individuals. Writers employ such specialized expressions to illuminate the character of their subjects.

Implicature and presupposition. Presupposition and implicature should be distinguished. The relationship between the speaker and the listener becomes intricate due to the inclusion of components of hidden meaning, in addition to propositions and presuppositions. One of these components of meaning is the representation of implicature, which conveys a concealed statement through the text.

The description of implicature in the text has two features: first, in most cases, implicature lacks an explicit verbal statement. In such situations, determining the presence of implicature in the text is achieved through logical analysis of propositions.

He tried to portray Saida as a stranger to these people: 'You didn't eat the food... You don't like their food... you don't like it!' (A. Qahhor)

In this text, the implicature 'you belong to a completely different category; that's why you don't like the collective farmer's food' is formed. During such instances, the crux of the analysis is linked to the speech situation. Participants in the conversation comprehend the essence of the

implicature or what is being referred to through judgments made with the aid of the speech situation and logical analysis.

In general, implicature, unlike presupposition, serves to covertly express the inner goals of speakers. Implicature is not always present in every text. Presupposition, on the other hand, can be determined through logical analysis of the semantic structure of any text. A presupposition does not hold the status of reported information, and it cannot be equated with the hidden content of an expression. Presupposition cannot be considered as one of the forms of hidden expression.

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